

Syntheses, spectral characterization and antimicrobial studies of the coordination compounds of the Schiff base containing diacetyl moiety

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Abstract : A new dibasic tetradentate ONNO donor Schiff base, LH₄ (**1**) has been synthesized by the nucleophilic addition reaction followed by the elimination of two water molecules between diacetyl and 3-ketobutanhydrazide (KBHz) in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The corresponding air-stable, non-electrolytic ($\Lambda_M = 2.4\text{--}8.9 \text{ mho cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in DMSO), six-coordinate coordination compounds, [M(LH₂)(H₂O)₂] (**2**) (where M = Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd) have also been synthesized by refluxing a MeOH solution of **1** and the appropriate ions in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The latter have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molecular weight, molar conductance, spectral (IR, reflectance, ¹H NMR) studies, TGA and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The molecular structure of the compounds have been optimized by MM2 calculations. They exhibit antimicrobial activities against Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*) and yeast (*S. cerevisiae*, *C. albicans*), however, they do not exhibit any activity against Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*).

Keywords : Coordination compounds, diacetyl, 3-ketobutanhydrazide, molecular modelling, MM2, octahedral compounds, Schiff base, spectral studies, thermogravimetric analysis.

Introduction

Coordination compounds of Schiff bases are widely used in food industry, dye industry, analytical chemistry, catalysis and also show fungicidal, agrochemical, anti-cancer and antitumor activities¹⁻⁴. Due to their excellent bioactivity, the hydrazones are widely used as insecticides, analytical agents and in medicines^{5,6}. A perusal of the literature indicates that much work has been reported on the Schiff bases containing the diacetyl moiety alone⁷⁻¹⁰ or hydrazone moiety alone¹¹⁻¹⁶, however, there is no report on the coordination compounds of the Schiff base derived from diacetyl and KBHz. Keeping in view, the above importance of compounds possessing the hydrazone moiety, we thought it worthwhile to synthesize and characterize the coordination compounds of **1** with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions. The present Schiff base and its corresponding coordination compounds have also been studied for their antimicrobial activities.

Results and discussion

The formation of orange coloured Schiff base, LH₄ (**1**) takes place by nucleophilic addition reaction between diacetyl and KBHz in EtOH followed by the elimination

of two water molecules as per Scheme 1.

A MeOH solution of **1** reacts with MeOH solution of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions and forms the corresponding coordination compounds (**2**), shown by Scheme 2.

The coordination compounds are air-stable. They get decomposed above 250 °C. They are fairly soluble in DMSO but sparingly soluble in H₂O, MeOH and EtOH. Their molar conductance data indicate their non-electrolytic nature (2.4–8.9 mho cm² mol⁻¹ in DMSO)¹⁷ (Table 1). The molecular weight measurements in diphenyl indicate their monomeric nature¹⁸.

Infrared spectral studies :

The IR spectra of KBHz, Schiff base (**1**) and its coordination compounds (**2**) were recorded in KBr and the prominent peaks are shown in Table 2. The Schiff base exhibits the $\nu(\text{O-H})$ (intramolecular H-bond), $\nu(\text{N-H})$ (intramolecular H-bond), $\nu(\text{C=O})$ (carbonyl) and $\nu(\text{C=N})$ (azomethine) stretches at 3131, 2923, 1714 and 1613 cm⁻¹, respectively. **1** occurs in both keto and enol form as evident by the presence of a band at 1714 cm⁻¹ and another band at 1285 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C=O})$ (carbonyl)

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Schiff base (1).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of 2.

and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (enolic) stretches, respectively. The occurrence of the former band at the same energy and the positive shift ($\sim 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the latter band in the coordination compounds indicate the non-involvement of ketonic O and involvement of enolic O atoms respectively towards coordination. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch of **1** occur-

Table 1. Analytical, colour, molar conductance ($\text{mho cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), mass spectral and molecular weight data of compounds

Sl. No.	Molecular formula	Colour	Λ_M	Mol. wt. Obsd. (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.) (%)			
					M	C	H	N
1.	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$	Orange	-	282 ^a (282)	-	51.22 (51.06)	6.42 (6.38)	19.79 (19.86)
2.	$\text{MnC}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Dark brown	7.1	359 ^b (371)	14.62 (14.80)	38.53 (38.81)	5.30 (5.39)	15.43 (15.09)
3.	$\text{CoC}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Brick red	2.4	394 ^b (375)	15.95 (15.73)	38.73 (38.40)	5.38 (5.33)	15.01 (14.93)
4.	$\text{NiC}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Green	7.2	353 ^b (374.7)	15.45 (15.67)	38.85 (38.43)	5.20 (5.34)	15.02 (14.94)
5.	$\text{ZnC}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Light orange	8.9	367 ^a (381.4)	17.37 (17.15)	38.53 (37.76)	5.17 (5.24)	14.73 (14.68)
6.	$\text{CdC}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	Orange	6.6	462 ^b (428.4)	26.45 (26.24)	33.47 (33.61)	4.88 (4.67)	13.33 (13.07)

Abbreviations : ^aMass spectral data and ^bRast method data.

Table 2. IR, reflectance spectral data (cm⁻¹) and magnetic moments of the coordination compounds

Sl. No.	Compound	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$	$\omega(\text{O}-\text{H})$	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	Magnetic moment
1.	1	1613	3131	–	–	–
2.	2 (M = Mn)	1571	3368	825	19685 27027 33333	5.85
3.	2 (M = Co)	1575	3368	812	20000 23529	4.70
4.	2 (M = Ni)	1570	3368	787	19531 26667	3.28
5.	2 (M = Zn)	1575	3338	801	–	Diamagnetic
6.	2 (M = Cd)	1568	3367	811	–	Diamagnetic

ring at 1613 cm⁻¹ undergoes a negative shift by 38–45 cm⁻¹ in **2** indicating the involvement of azomethine N atom towards coordination¹⁹. This downward shift is expected due to the reduction in electron density in azomethine link on compound formation. The appearance of a medium intense broad band between 3368–3338 cm⁻¹ due to the $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ stretch, another band of weak intensity between 787–825 cm⁻¹ due to $\omega(\text{O}-\text{H})$ (rocking) modes support the presence of coordinated H₂O molecules in the present compounds²⁰. The hydrazidic N atom does not take place in coordination, as evident by the presence of $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ stretch at the same energy (2923–2928 cm⁻¹) both in **1** and **2**. The appearance of two new non-ligand bands, one between 562–620 cm⁻¹ and another between 470–517 cm⁻¹ due to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ stretches respectively, in **2** supports the involvement of enolic O and azomethine N atoms in coordination²¹. The increasing order of the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N}) < \nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ is as expected according to the greater dipole moment change in the M–O vibrations, greater electronegativity of O atom than N atom and shorter M–O bond length than M–N bond length^{21,22}.

Reflectance spectral studies :

[Mn(LH₂)(H₂O)₂] shows absorption bands at 19685, 27027, 33333, 37593, 44444 and 46512 cm⁻¹ due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)(\nu_1)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)(\nu_2)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)(\nu_3)$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ intraligand transitions²³, respectively. [Co(LH₂)(H₂O)₂] shows absorption bands 20000, 23529, 33898, 41494 and 49020 cm⁻¹ due to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\nu_2)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow$

π^* charge transfer transitions²⁴, respectively. [Ni(LH₂)(H₂O)₂] shows absorption bands at 19531, 26667, 37594 and 48077 cm⁻¹ due to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ charge transfer transitions²⁵, respectively. The transitions in above coordination compounds are consistent with their octahedral geometry^{26,27}.

Mass spectra :

The Electron Ionization Mass Spectra (EIMS) of **1** and [Zn(LH₂)(H₂O)₂] were recorded on Waters Micromass Q-ToF Micro-mass spectrometer. The prominent fragmentation peaks in **1** observed at $m/z = 282, 265, 191, 168, 141$ and 126 are tentatively assigned to $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{OH}]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$ and $[\text{M}-\text{C}_7\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$ respectively. The prominent fragmentation peaks in [Zn(LH₂)(H₂O)₂] observed at $m/z = 381, 366, 345, 325, 269, 253, 188, 152$ and 125 are tentatively assigned to $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{CH}_3]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-2\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{C}_3\text{H}_4\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{ZnC}_5\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, $[\text{M}-\text{ZnC}_5\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4]^{+\bullet}$ and $[\text{M}-\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4]^{+\bullet}$ respectively. The above observed peaks in [Zn(LH₂)(H₂O)₂] support the proposed 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the compound.

¹H NMR studies :

The ¹H NMR spectra of **1** and [Cd(LH₂)(H₂O)₂] were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆. The chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm downfield δ from TMS²⁸. The Schiff base (**1**) exhibits a singlet at δ 2.17 ppm due to methyl protons (diacetyl moiety), a singlet at δ 2.38 ppm due to methyl protons (KBHz moiety), a doublet at δ 4.48 ppm due to

methine protons, a doublet at δ 5.81 ppm due to –NH protons and a broad signal at δ 11.21 ppm due to enolic O–H proton. The absence of the resonance signal due to the enolic proton in $[\text{Cd}(\text{LH}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ indicates the deprotonation of the –OH group of the ligand followed by involvement in coordination. The appearance of new strong intense peak at δ 3.44 ppm is tentatively assigned to the protons of coordinated H_2O molecules²⁹.

Thermogravimetric studies (TGA) :

The thermogram of $[\text{Cd}(\text{LH}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ was recorded in nitrogen at a heating rate of 10 °C/min over a temperature range of 50–400 °C. The compound decomposes in three stages. The first stage corresponds to the loss of one coordinated H_2O molecule³⁰ between 100–150 °C (Calcd. 4.2%; Obsd. 4.0%). The second stage occurs between 150–350 °C corresponding to the loss of remaining coordinated H_2O molecule plus organic skeleton, $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{N}_2$ (Calcd. 23.4%; Obsd. 23.0%). The third step occurs between 350–400 °C. CdO is the final product.

Magnetic measurements :

The room temperature magnetic moment of $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ is 5.85 B.M., lying in normal range suggests the magnetically dilute octahedral behaviour of Mn^{II} ions³¹. The magnetic moment of $[\text{Co}(\text{LH}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ is 4.70 B.M., also favours the octahedral behaviour of Co^{II} ions³¹. The magnetic moment of $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ is 3.28 B.M., indicating octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ions³¹. Rest of the coordination compounds are diamagnetic as expected.

Molecular modelling :

The 3D molecular modelling of suggested structure of the coordination compounds were performed by using MM2 programme contained under CS Chem 3D Pro-14 program package. The *cis* and *trans* position of the ligand moiety and H_2O as ligand was assured through the manipulation and modification of the molecular coordinates to obtain reasonable low energy molecular geometries. The potential energy of the molecule was the sum of following terms $E = E_{\text{str}} + E_{\text{ang}} + E_{\text{tor}} + E_{\text{VDW}} + E_{\text{oop}} + E_{\text{ele}}$ where all E's represent the energy values corresponding to the given types of interaction. The subscripts str, ang, tor, VDW, oop and ele denote bond stretching, angle bending, torsion deformation, Van der Waals interaction, out of plain bending and electronic interaction, respectively. The minimum energy calculated using MM2 programme for *cis* stereochemistry of Mn^{II} compound was 331.3641 kcal/mol while for *trans* stereochemistry was 298.0795 kcal/mol. Molecular modelling showed octahedral geometry and *trans* stereochemistry for Mn^{II} compound³².

Antimicrobial studies :

The Schiff base and their coordination compounds were screened for their antimicrobial and antifungal activities. The compounds possessed variable activities against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*. The ligand and its Cd^{II} compound showed activity against *S. cerevisiae* and *C. albicans*. All the compounds were inactive against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. Positive controls produced significantly sized inhibition zones against the above microbes, however,

Table 3. *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of synthetic chemical compounds through agar well diffusion method

Sl. No.	Compound	Diameter of growth of inhibition zone (mm) ^a					
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1.	1	14.6	16.3	–	–	14.3	15.6
2.	2 (M = Mn)	15.3	17.6	–	–	–	–
3.	2 (M = Co)	16.3	17.3	–	–	–	–
4.	2 (M = Ni)	15.6	16.3	–	–	–	–
5.	2 (M = Zn)	13.6	15.6	–	–	–	–
6.	2 (M = Cd)	21.3	23.6	–	–	16.3	16.6
7.	<i>Ciprofloxacin</i>	26.6	24.0	25.0	22.0	–	–
8.	<i>Amphotericin-B</i>	–	–	–	–	19.3	16.6

Abbreviations : ^avalues, including diameter of the well (8 mm), are means of three replicates.

– = No activity.

Table 4. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of compounds by using modified agar well diffusion method

Sl. No.	Compound	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1.	1	256	128	256	128
2.	2 (M = Mn)	128	128	–	–
3.	2 (M = Co)	163	128	–	–
4.	2 (M = Ni)	128	128	–	–
5.	2 (M = Zn)	256	128	–	–
6.	2 (M = Cd)	32	16	128	128
7.	<i>Ciprofloxacin</i>	6.25	6.25	–	–
8.	<i>Amphotericin-B</i>	–	–	12.5	12.5

negative control produced no observable inhibitory effect against any of these microbes. The Cd^{II} coordination compound was found to be the most effective against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* (Tables 3 and 4). We hope that the present Cd^{II} coordination compound may be used as an antimicrobial agent in pharmaceutical industry, after testing its toxicity to human beings.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Diacetyl [Aldrich], manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate, cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate, nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate, ethyl acetoacetate, hydrazine hydrate [Fisher Scientific], zinc(II) acetate dihydrate, cadmium(II) acetate dihydrate, DMSO, DMF, MeOH, EtOH, 1,4-dioxane and THF [Ranbaxy] were used as received for syntheses. KBHz was synthesized as per the method reported earlier³³. The molecular structure of the compounds were optimized by

Fig. 1. Bar chart indicating the diameter of growth of inhibition zone for compounds/standard against various microbes. Abbreviations : Sa : *S. aureus*, Bs : *B. subtilis*, Sc : *S. cerevisiae*, Ca : *C. albicans*, Ec : *E. coli*, Pa : *P. aeruginosa*.

CS Chem 3D Pro-14 program package.

Analytical and physical measurements :

The estimation of metal contents, spectral studies (IR, reflectance, ^1H NMR) and the magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by the methods reported earlier¹⁹. The melting points of compounds were determined on digital melting point apparatus (Stuart SMP-40). The molar conductances of coordination compounds in DMSO were carried out using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge (Model CL01-02A) and a dip type cell calibrated with KCl solution. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen contents of the coordination compounds were estimated on a FLASH EA 1112 CHNS (O) analyzer. The IR spectra of ligand and its coordination compounds were recorded in KBr ($4000\text{--}250\text{ cm}^{-1}$) on a Fourier Transform Infra Red Spectrometer (Model RZX, Perkin-Elmer, SAIF, Chandigarh). The reflectance spectra of (**2**) (M = Mn, Co, Ni) were recorded on a Hitachi-330 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra of the ligand and its corresponding Cd^{II} coordination compound were recorded

Fig. 2. Bar chart indicating minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) for compounds/standard against various microbes.

Fig. 3. Proposed structure of 2 (M= Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd).

Fig. 4. Optimized structure of $[Mn(LH_2)(H_2O)_2]$ (*cis*).

on an Avance-II Bruker FT NMR spectrometer at 400 MHz, using DMSO as a solvent and TMS as an internal standard. The mass spectra of ligand and its corresponding Zn^{II} coordination compound were recorded on Waters Micromass Q-ToF Micro-mass spectrometer. Agar well diffusion method was used to perform the antimicrobial studies of ligand and their coordination compounds. The bacteria were subcultured on nutrient agar, whereas the yeasts on malt agar.

Fig. 5. Optimized structure of $[Mn(LH_2)(H_2O)_2]$ (*trans*).

Antibacterial activity :

The Schiff base and its coordination compounds were screened for the evaluation of their antimicrobial activities against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. cerevisiae* and *C. albicans*. All the microbial cultures were adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standards which were visually comparable to a microbial suspension of approximately 1.5×10^8 cfu/mL. 20 mL of agar medium was poured into each Petri plate and the plates were swabbed with 100 μ L inocula of the test microorganisms and kept for 15 min for adsorption. Using sterile cork borer of 8 mm diameter, wells were bored into the seeded agar plates and these were loaded with a 100 μ L volume with concentration of 2.0 mg/mL of each compound reconstituted in DMSO. All the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The antimicrobial activity of each compound was evaluated by measuring the zone of growth inhibition against the organisms with zone reader (HiAntibiotic zone scale). DMSO was used as a negative control, whereas *Ciprofloxacin* was used as positive control for bacteria and *Amphotericin-B* for yeast. This procedure was performed in three replicate plates for each organism³⁴.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of compounds :

MIC is the lowest concentration of an antimicrobial compound that inhibits the visible growth of a microorganism after overnight incubation. MIC of the various

compounds against bacterial and yeast strains was tested through a modified agar well diffusion method³⁴. In this method, a two-fold serial dilution of each compound was prepared by first reconstituting the compound in DMSO followed by dilution in sterile distilled water to achieve a decreasing concentration range of 512 to 1 µg/mL. A 100 µL volume of each dilution was introduced into wells (in triplicate) in the agar plates already seeded with 100 µL of standardized inoculum (1066 cfu/mL) of the test microbial strain. All the test plates were incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 24 h and observed for the inhibition zones. MIC was recorded for each test organism. *Ciprofloxacin* and *Amphotericin-B* were used as positive control, while DMSO as negative control.

Synthesis of 3-ketobutanehydrazide (KBHz) :

The title compound was synthesized according to literature procedure³³.

Synthesis of 1 :

Diacetyl (0.43 g, 5 mmol) and KBHz (1.16 g, 10 mmol) were refluxed in EtOH (50 mL) on a water bath for 2–3 h. The orange coloured compound separated out was suction filtered, washed with and recrystallized from EtOH and then dried as mentioned above. Yield 70%, m.p. 135 °C; Anal. Calcd. (%) for C₁₂H₁₈N₄O₄; (282) : C, 51.06; H, 6.38; N, 19.86. Found (%) : C, 51.22; H, 6.42; N, 19.79; IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) : 3131 (OH) (intramolecular H-bond), 2923 (N–H) intramolecular H-bond, 1714 (C=O) carbonyl, 1613 (C=N) azomethine, 1285 (C–O) enolic, 1015 (N–N); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : s, singlet; d, doublet; m, multiplet; b, broad; 2.17 (6H, s, -CH₃), 2.38 (6H, s, -CH₃ attached with -C=O group), 4.48 (2H, d, -CH), 5.81 (2H, d, -NH), 11.21 (2H, b, enolic-OH).

Synthesis of 2 :

A MeOH solution (~30 mL) of appropriate metal acetate (5 mmol) was added to MeOH solution (~50 mL) of 1 (1.41 g, 5 mmol) with constant stirring. The solution was refluxed on a water bath for 3–4 h and solid residue obtained was suction filtered, washed with MeOH and dried as mentioned above. Yield : 60–80%. The compounds are stable up to 250 °C and get decomposed above this temperature.

Conclusion

On the basis of analytical data, valence requirements, conductance, spectral studies and magnetic susceptibility measurements, it is proposed that the Schiff base (1) behaves as a dibasic tetradentate ONNO donor ligand in these coordination compounds coordinating through its both azomethine N and enolic O atoms. The coordination compounds of Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} are paramagnetic, while rest of the compounds are diamagnetic. The data suggest an octahedral structure for all the coordination compounds with *trans* stereochemistry. They show significant increased antimicrobial activities as compared to the free Schiff base. After testing their toxicity, these may be used in pharmaceutical industry as an antimicrobial agent for mankind.

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